

Removal and cleaning of two artworks made out of tiles

(a case study)

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Abstract

Art in architecture has been placed since the very early history of architecture, while publicly financed art in architecture is a young phenomenon dating back to the early 20th century and, in the case of former Czechoslovakia to the WWII period. This article then comprises two case studies on artworks placed in buildings under the 4 % to Art Act. Both artworks were located in the 1980s in Prague, the Czech Republic (formerly Czechoslovakia). We were allowed to remove both from the buildings, which had to be reconstructed or demolished. The first removal we did in 2020. It consisted of chamotte tiles, and Lubomír Šilar made it. The second was white tiles with colored imprint by Stanislav Holý, and we were removing it in 2024.

In both cases, we had only two days to document and remove the artworks. For the work, we have used both electric and hand tools. After removal, many tiles had adhesive and mortar on the back, which we have partly removed to store them better. Our findings show that it is possible to remove such artworks in a shorter period of time if there are enough skilled workers and sound equipment. It is also essential to have the mindset that tiles will crack anyway, and also, in both cases, some tiles have cracked in different phases of the projects. We would appreciate more published studies on tile physics and internal pressures to improve other methodologies next time. Still, we figured out that for tile removal, we would need long, flat, and strong metal toll as tiles were big, and diamond grinding discs with an angle grinder, which can regulate RPM, were the best choice to remove excessive mortar from the back. The first artwork is currently in the museum collections; the second is stored in our archive for future reuse and further research.

Introduction

Art in architecture

Art has been installed in architecture since ancient times, but only the investors have changed. At the beginning of the 20th century, the state joined the donor's side and gradually created legislation for these processes. In 1921, a government mural painting program was created in Mexico, which inspired the Federal Art Project in the USA in 1934. The latter introduced the mechanism of a percentage of the realization of the building whose investor is the state for artworks permanently installed in this building.¹ This mechanism was then inspired by other countries, such as France, where the first attempts were made to enforce a similar law in 1936 and 1937, but it was only possible after the Second World War.²

Former Czechoslovakia, introduced the so-called Four percent law³ in 1965 but already invested in art in architecture before. This was due to political changes and nationalization, which caused private investors to disappear completely.⁴ For example, post-war Poland, reconstruction of cities destroyed by the war, including new construction, took place first. The original decorations of the buildings were restored, and new ones were added. Gradually, relief, specifically mosaic, gained popularity. When the massive construction of schools took place, it was precisely the mosaic that was widely used as a decorative element.⁵

In Czechoslovakia, as part of the Four percent law, the works of a large number of artists were realized, including those who were not on good terms with the regime at a certain stage of their lives.⁶ In the 1970s and 1980s alone, at least 16,500 artworks were installed this way.⁷ However, the situation changed in the 1990s, when after the fall of the totalitarian regime, a private investor appeared again, and at the same time, the 4% law ceased to apply at the beginning of this decade.⁸ Private investors no longer invested the same amount as the state. On the contrary, building reconstruction began, with which this art gradually began to disappear.

1 Pavel Karous, 'Umění v hotelu ČSSR. Systém osazování výtvarného umění v architektuře na Západě a v ČSSR', in *Hotel Praha* (Prague: Bigg Boss, 2019), 60–75. (Czech)

2 Marie-Laure Viale, 'La Cité Scolaire de Saint-Nazaire (1953-1970), Récit d'un Programme d'œuvres « 1 % » à Travers Son Réseau d'acteurs', *In Situ*, no. 32 (4 July 2017), <https://doi.org/10.4000/insitu.15110>. (French)

3 In fact, it was not a law, but a government resolution.

4 Karous, 'Umění v hotelu ČSSR'.

5 Sebastian Wróblewski, 'Nowa sztuka w nowym społeczeństwie. Wybrane aspekty sztuki towarzyszącej architekturze z drugiej połowy xx wieku w Polsce.', *Architektura v perspektivě 2016*, 1 January 2016, 243–52. (Polish)

6 Examples are the sculptors Sylva Lacinová and Olbram Zoubek. They became inconvenient to the regime after 1968, they were banned from exhibiting, but their works continued to enter architecture.

7 Jan Lochman, 'Database of the Collaboration between an Artist and an Architect' (Zenodo, 17 November 2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10149620>.

8 Pavel Karous, 'Procento na umění (díl první)', accessed 3 September 2024, <https://www.vetrelciavolavky.cz/texty/procento-na-umeni-dil-prvni>. (English)

Removal and storage of artistically designed tiles

Very little academic literature is written in English on removing valuable tiles and saving them, but when something does appear, the details still need to be included.⁹ The knowledge of how to remove and clean tiles is maintained among restorers. According to Mendes, however, this field does not offer formal education.¹⁰ Restaurateurs thus pass this information on to each other orally or in printed form or develop their procedures. Gjurič states, for example, that rich documentation was taken during the reconstruction of the Municipal House in Prague, the Czech Republic.¹¹ The restoration work in this listed building also included the removal of tightly glued tiles from the beginning of the 20th century. However, we were unable to find documentation of these procedures. In the same way, we did not have the opportunity to study popular literature written in Spanish and Portuguese, which was supposed to be devoted to the issue of scanning tiles. We only got one mention in the popular article in Czech language and unofficial instructional videos on YouTube.

Paine states¹² that turned diamond tools were used to remove the tiles. Interesting videos on YouTube then recommend cutting the joints between the tiles. In most cases, this is done with a diamond tool attached to a power tool;¹³¹⁴¹⁵ in one case, the grout is crushed by the impact of a mason's chisel.¹⁶ The scanning is ensured by successively tapping a flat iron tool behind the tile from different sides. All the cited sources, however, illustrate this on floor tiles.

Mendes' research yielded only general statistics showing that most surveyed cleaned mechanically or chemically - i.e., by immersion in a solvent.¹⁷ Specific procedures, however, were not documented. Because of the need for more information about the procedures for scanning and cleaning tiles in the academia, we decided to publish our experiences and findings in English.

Materials

In this study, we describe methods used to remove, partially clean, and store two artworks made out of tiles from the wall. In both cases, it was a coincidence that we got information about the plan to

9 W have been searching in the Web of Science and ProQuest using the terms "tile removal" or "tile conservation".

10 Marta T Mendes et al., 'In Situ Preservation and Restoration of Architectural Tiles, Materials and Procedures: Results of an International Survey', 2015.

11 Alexander Gjurič, 'Odstrojení jako součást přípravy obnovy stavební památky', in *Regenerace historických budov, sídel a krajiny, ochrana památek*, 1998, 166–71. (Czech)

12 Shelley Reisman Paine, 'The Treatment and Installation of a Frederick and Agnes Rhead Ceramic Tile Fireplace Surround', *Journal of the American Institute for Conservation* 47, no. 1 (January 2008): 41–49, <https://doi.org/10.1179/019713608806112241>.

13 AZ DIY Guy, 'Removing a Floor Tile without Breaking it - Re-Use Discontinued Tile', (YouTube, 2019), online: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EW6TxzLG6dQ>

14 C.L.S. ALL-IN-ONE, 'How to remove Ceramic & Stone Tiles for Repair or Demo purposes', (YouTube, 2020), online: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p7cBazK4jrs>

15 Rachel Martinelli, 'Quickly Remove Floor Tiles without Breaking', (YouTube, 2018), online: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TcfQP2-ZWdY>

16 SolarGirl Homestead, 'How to remove tile | Without breaking it', (YouTube, 2017), online: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PImEP7fRNgQ>

17 Mendes et al., 'In Situ Preservation and Restoration of Architectural Tiles, Materials and Procedures: Results of an International Survey'.

damage these artworks. In both cases, we had only two days to remove these artworks. That's why we didn't have much time to do further documentation and preparation of the project.

Artwork by Lubomír Šilar

In 2020, we have removed the ceramic relief created by Lubomír Šilar,¹⁸ which was attached to the exterior facade of a building in the district of Letňany, Prague, the Czech Republic.

The eight to three meters long relief made of ochre grainy porous tiles holds an abstract motive, where one can recognize a book, a bird, a flower, a leaf, and a lyre all surrounded or covered by horizontal grooves that resemble rain or shade of darkness. This motive was in the middle and surrounded by plain tiles (Figure 1). One of the modeled tiles holds a signature, “ŠILAR 81”, which indicates it was created in 1981

by Lubomír Šilar. The available literature also supports this.¹⁹ Modeled 38.5 x 38.5-centimeter tiles²⁰ are covered by dark and white glaze, while the surrounding plain tiles have a light brown ochre color, which is also the material's color. However they look plain from the distance, they are also cover by small horizontal regular grooves and irregular grooves perpendicular to them, but much more shallow than the ones of the motive (Figure 2). Finally, there were 160 tiles altogether partially embedded under the surrounding plaster.

Even though the author is recognized amongst the art community, and his works are in multiple national and foreign galleries and museums, this artwork did not have any kind of state protection, nor was it recognized by the owner to survive. The reason for its removal by the owner of the building was to build there a new entrance to the building. So we agreed with the owner to take it down and thus acquired the work in our ownership. Otherwise, it will be removed as construction waste.

When we arrived on the scene, some tiles had already been removed and scattered around the work. Some had also been damaged to pieces. We were provided with a 230 V electricity socket and scaffolding.

Artwork by Stanislav Holý

Later, in 2024, we were informed about an ongoing demolition of another building in Prague, and we figured out that there were still valuable artworks. Again, we contacted the owner, and we were given two days to remove them.

Figure 1. Artwork by Lubomír Šilar before its removal

Figure 2: An example of a "plain" tile from Lubomír Šilar's artwork

¹⁸ Later in the text, this is referred as “first artwork”, or “Šilar’s work”.

¹⁹ *Spolupráce výtvarníka s architektem: Přehled prací za rok 1981* (Dílo, n.d.), 24. (Czech)

²⁰ However, some tiles were not exact squares, and some of their sides were slightly shorter or longer than 38.5 cm.

In this case the artwork from 1989 by Stanislav Holý²¹²² consisted of three separate artworks located in the reception of the building.²³ They consisted of industrially made wall white glazed tiles with the color artwork painted over. All three were of the same kind, an abstraction with letters with feet, flowers, leaves, and rainbows (Figure 3). Such an artistic concept was typical for this author and it is possible to meet such work elsewhere in architecture or as decoration for television programs for children.

Figure 3. Artwork A by Stanislav Holý after the removal

One artwork was on the left from the entrance to the reception. This artwork was on the walls around the bi-fold doors, so its center was missing and partially obscured by the reception door frame. By this frame of the door, there was one tile holding the inscription "STANISLAV HOLÝ, ©1987/88," which indicates the creation year. The signature was accompanied by the stamp with letters "PORCELAINE FINE DE BOHEME, EPIAG D.F., CZECHOSLOVAKIA, CARSLBAD, ANTONIA". Moreover, between this stamp and the author's signature by the copyright mark, there were two pink flowers with yellow central parts surrounded by green leaves and two smaller flowers with blue petals and yellow central parts. The style of this decoration was more realistic than that of the artworks. This work is referred to in the text as the artwork of A. The other one was on the opposite side in the corner on two perpendicular walls. This one is referred to in the text as artwork B. The last piece was on the wall in front of the entrance to the reception, and this one is referred to as artwork C. Figure 4 shows the floor plan of the reception area with the layout of the artwork.

Figure 4. Floorplan of the reception with three artworks by Stanislav Holý highlighted

21 *Spolupráce výtvarníka s architektem: Přehled prací za rok 1989* (Dílo, n.d.), 65. (Czech)

22 Further, it is referred to as "second artwork".

23 Due to the license of this document and Czech copyright, we cannot present a photograph of the interior artwork here. Thus, we present parts of this artwork after the removal and situation drawing instead.

A metal bar was screwed into the tiles in the upper part of all the works. Some tiles had a chipped edge or corner, some were stuck with signs, and one tile was cracked. In the vicinity of the artworks, white tiles were placed, or doors and windows were located. The joints between the tiles were filled with white grout, but the joints were not the same size everywhere. Most tiles were rectangles with dimensions of 30 x 40 centimeters, but there were also square and longitudinal tiles. On the floor, gray glazed tiles were leaning against the wall, which came from the cladding behind the interior door and behind the outer door at the entrance to the reception. These were 0.9 cm thick and the same size as the tiles from the interior of the building.

Artwork A consisted of 77 colored tiles, and with the hole for the door, the extension was 287 x 490 cm. The B consisted of 54 colored tiles with dimensions of 291 x 171 cm per one side and 291 x 147 cm per the perpendicular site. For the last artwork, C, 95 tiles held color, and the dimensions were 289 x 460 cm.

Tools for breaking up grout between tiles

We were not breaking up grout between tiles in the case of Lubomír Šilar's work, so we have not used any tools for that.

In the case of Stanislav Holý's artwork, we have tested a wider range of tools (Figure 5). To break up the grout between the tiles, we used a carbide joint cleaner, scribe pen, a snap blade utility knife, a putty knife, a mason's chisel, an old screwdriver, and of course a hammer. Furthermore, a Bosch AdvanceGrind 18-angle grinder with a diamond cutting disc with a diameter of 125 mm, a maximum working depth of 20 mm, and a maximum speed of 12,200 RPM. For this, we had four Bosch rechargeable batteries. Two 18 V 4 Ah (PBA W-C 1 607 A35 OPB) and two 2.5 Ah (PBA W-B 2 607 337 199). Two Bosch AL 1830 CV battery chargers were used to charge them.

Tools for tile removal

For the removal of Lubomír Šilar's work, we used Bosch PBH 2100 RE jackhammer with a chisel of 210 mm in length and 40 mm wide. We made two long wooden wedges on the site. The company, which was reconstructing the building, provided electricity via a 230 V socket and scaffolding.

For the removal of Stanislav Holý's glazed tiles, we tested the following tools: various types of putty knives, which differ mainly in their width, mason's chisels of various widths, a scraper

Figure 5. From the left: carbide joint cleaner, scribe pen, putty knife, old screwdriver, two mason's chisels, angle grinder, and batteries. There is also a hammer, battery charger, and diamond-cutting disc

Figure 6. From the left: three putty knives, three mason's chisels, a hammer, and a glass suction cup on the top

with a sharpened edge, a hammer, and a glass suction cup (Figure 6). In addition, we had two double-sided aluminum ladders with a height of 6490 mm.

Mortar and adhesive grinding tools

We used the following tools to remove excess mortar and adhesive from the tiles: Makita GA5030R Angle Grinder, DeWalt DWE4257 Angle Grinder, Bosch GBR 15 CAG Concrete Grinder, Bosch diamond grinding disc 2 608 601 762 125 mm of diameter, dust extraction cover for angle grinders MAGG 125-115 mm with brush ring, vacuum cleaner Karcher WD 3, mason's chisels, cordless drill MyProject IAN JOZ-YFT56-212V, wire wheel, knotted wire cup brush, wire brush, P 40 sandpaper for metal, and a hammer (Figure 7). We also used citric acid and a pressure hose.

Figure 7. From the left: mason's chisel, hammer, wire wheel, knotted wire cup brush, cordless drill, wire brush, dust extraction cover, diamond grinding disc, DeWalt angle grinder

Storage

For storage purposes, we bought two 180x90 cm metal shelving racks with a 175-kilogram load capacity per shelf, got cardboard paper from old boxes, glasses with lids, bubble wrap, and a plastic box.

Personal protection

Traditional protective equipment, such as a hard hat, safety glasses, FFP2 respirator, half-face air-purifying respirator, leather mason's gloves, ear protector, and sturdy hard-toe construction shoes, was used for tile removal and grinding.

Methods

Breaking up grout between tiles

In the case of Lubomír Šilar's work, we were not breaking grout.

For Stanislav Holý's artwork, we conducted a comprehensive testing process. We began with the joint compound and then systematically tested various removal methods. These included cutting the joints with a carbide joint cleaner, a scribe pen, a snap-blade utility knife, a putty knife, and an angle grinder. We then moved on to the chipping method, tapping with a hammer on tools such as a scribe pen, a putty knife, a mason's chisel, and a screwdriver. This thorough testing process instilled confidence in our approach.

Since we did not have a source of electricity available at the site, one of the workers had to take the accumulators to be charged to the place where we had arranged it, while also taking away the removed tiles and bringing any consumables.

Methods of tile removal

In the case of the artwork by Lubomír Šilar, we used a jackhammer, which we gradually drove behind the tiles and broke them off. Two long wooden wedges were inserted into the holes made by the jackhammer. Two people always worked on one tile. One carefully drove the hammer behind the tile, and the other secured it with his hands so it would not fall. It has always progressed from top to bottom through the ranks.

The removed tiles were interlaced with cardboard paper and taken to storage. The shards were put into cardboard banana boxes together from the tiles from which they were peeled. Tiles removed by the company worker the day before were also loaded, and shards were dug out from piles of rubble.

For the tile removal of the second artwork, we were always working from top to bottom by columns or rows. As both artworks were almost three meters from the floor, when working on the tiles on top, we used double-sided aluminium ladders.

We used two primary methods to separate the tiles from the substrate. One consisted of jamming the chisel into the mortar behind the tile and gradually moving under the tile. The second method involved gently jamming the putty knife and mason's chisel or scraper with a sharpened edge directly behind the tile, i.e., between the tile and the adhesive.

Whilescraper with a sharpened edge was sufficient to remove tile; when using flat putty knives, inserting far more knives under the tile (Figure 8) or even mason's chisels was necessary. Of course, the work was easier when there were one or two free sides to get behind the tile.

Figure 8. Inserting putty knives under the tile

The workers gradually jammed tools under the tiles, monitoring the tension in the tiles so as not to damage them. Therefore, it involved repeatedly jamming the tools into various places behind the

tiles, pulling them out, and jamming deeper again. In some cases, there was even gentle prying. Some tools were left behind in the mined tile and served as wedges.

One of the masons also tried to speed up the removal of three tiles in a row at once so that he did not cut them together at the point of connection with the joint compound and only cut them with a chisel. When removing it from the wall, the second worker then had to secure a row of tiles with his hands.

We used a glass suction cup to hold the tiles in one case.

In Šilar's work, masons were working together, removing one tile at a time; in the case of Holý's work, most of the time, masons worked alone. The reason to work together on Šilar's work was that the removed tiles, together with adhesive and mortar residues, could have up to ten kilograms, while glazed tiles had about three kilograms. One worker could not remove them alone.

Removing excessive mortar and adhesives

In the case of Šilar's work, we were left with just four tiles or part of tiles because other tiles were given to the collections of Lanškroun Municipal Museum before we could test the mortar removal. On Šilar's tiles, we have tested only chipping with mason's chisel and grinding diamond discs with DeWalt DWE4257 Angle Grinder and Bosch GBR 15 CAG Concrete Grinder.

In the case of Holý's work, we first removed stickers, older glue, and impurities by rubbering with a regular pencil eraser or carefully peeling with a putty knife while heating with a heating gun. Some of the tiles still had the metal lath attached to them and the dowels in them, which we had to carefully remove, too.

Figure 9. Scratching yellow adhesive with a putty knife and wetting it with water

We have divided tiles into three categories. First were those with a thin layer of adhesive, second with adhesive and some parts of mortar, and third with a high amount of mortar. The last two categories were left for machine grinding using diamond rotary discs, while those with just a thin layer of adhesive were partially cleaned by other means. This included hitting it with a putty knife – in the case of grayish adhesives, which were hard, while the yellowish ones were less hard, and the adhesive could be removed with scratching by a putty knife (Figure 9). Some tiles were soaked in water for several hours, others we soaked before each scraping of the adhesives. When using putty knives, we often had to sharpen them as their edges were smoothed out quite fast. Sharpening putty knives was done by cutting a piece of it with a metal disk of an angle grinder.

We also tried other means to clean tiles from the first and second categories, like rotary wire brushes, citric acid, and pressurized water. Small pieces with a small amount of adhesive were prone to sand by sandpaper.

In the case of the use of diamond disks in rotary grinders, we have started with the concrete grinder Bosch GBR 15 CAG, which had a constant RPM of 9300, but we returned it because we had

borrowed it for a fee and did not want to damage it. Then we bought our Bosch diamond grinding disc and continued with the Makita GA5030R angle grinder. After they broke, we bought a DeWalt DWE4257 angle grinder, which was advertised to have protection against overheating and dust entering inside.

One tile we ground on an uneven floor broke. Thus, we decided to continue on an even surface with a height that is comfortable for a worker. So, we prepared the workspace by covering everything with plastic film. Subsequently, we used a 1980s ROMO washing machine as a working table, on which we also placed two ten-centimeter polystyrene foam sheets. We covered them with a moving blanket and glued everything with duct tape (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Grinding mortar from a tile with a diamond disk attached to an angle grinder

We started with the model of one person grinding and the other observing, and then we continued with two people actively cooperating. It means one person was only grinding, while the other was placing tiles for grinding, removing those that were needed, and controlling the vacuum cleaner.

To prevent any movement, the other person used two 20 cm wooden prisms to hold small tile pieces and shards in place (Figure 11).

On the sanders, we had a dust extraction cover and a vacuum cleaner connected to it. For reasons of strength and isolation of leaking dust, we covered the joint with duck tape. In the vacuum cleaner, we regularly checked the filter's clogging and, if necessary, shake it. We gradually replaced the bags.

Figure 11. Reconstruction of the process of holding and grinding mortar on tiny shards

Makita had a constant speed of about 11,000 RPM, but with the high amount of material, it slowed down and often heated. Before working with the DeWalt grinder, we chipped excessive mortar by hand with mason's chisels and putty knives—but not all, as we were afraid to break tiles.

When using the DeWalt grinder, which offers adjustable speeds, we carefully selected the speed based on the material being sanded. For softer materials like mortar, we opted for lower speeds of 4,240 and 5,680 RPM to ensure efficient material removal. We chose a higher speed of 7,120 RPM for harder materials such as cement-like adhesives. Lower rotation speeds were also used when sanding yellow adhesives and smaller pieces and shards. We reduced the speed to 2,800 RPM for the smallest shards for safety reasons.

Methods of storage

Before putting them on the shelves, we had to fold the rack according to the instructions and sand off their tongues, which could not be slid in. Subsequently, we laid a maximum of 8 tiles on the individual shelves, which we laid with pre-cut cardboard paper (Figure 12).

We laid the tiles so the individual works were together and the white and gray tiles separated. We put the pieces of cracked tiles together. The method of laying tiles is reverse down, face down, reverse down, face down, i.e., that the tiles optically fit back and front.

We stored the chopped mortar fragments in jars, labeling them with details of what they were, where they came from, and when they were stored. These labeled jars were then placed in a resealable box for safekeeping.

Figure 12. Tiles stored on the shelves

Human health protection procedures

Every worker used the protection equipment characterized above. We also used vacuum cleaners to remove excessive dust or wash it away from our tools after work.

Results

Disruption of the grout between the tiles

In the case of Lubomír Šilar's work, we were not disrupting grout between tiles. The other artwork's fastest and cleanest results were done with a diamond disc and angle grinder. Carbide joint cleaner also worked, but it was much slower than an angle grinder and would not fit into some very narrow joints. A putty knife, a mason's chisel, and an old screwdriver only worked if they were hammered. If we tried to cut with them, the effect was bad. However, the worker still had to monitor the width of the joint and choose a thinner working tool; otherwise, there was a risk of pieces of tiles breaking off. It was entirely insufficient to cut the joints with a scribe pen. Finally, most of the joint grout was disrupted by the angle grinder.

Tile removal

Both methods described above, which were used to remove tiles of Lubomír Šilar and Stanislav Holý artworks, yielded the removal of tiles. In the case of Šilar's artwork, 40 % of the tiles cracked during the removal process and 12 % during the removal of Holý's artwork, respectively. In the first case, tiles were cracking during the whole removal process, while during the second artwork removal, most of the tiles cracked at the beginning – i.e., when a worker was starting at all or starting with a new artwork.

Figure 13. The example of mortar residues on the tile from Holý's work. Yellow is the adhesive; gray is the mortar with a nail

The number of pieces per cracked tile was higher for Šilar's artwork. In the case of glazed tiles removal, most of the pieces cracked once or twice, making two to three pieces.

The majority of Šilar's tiles were retrieved with an adhesive, mortar, and even a metal net; in the case of the other removal, about 30 % were removed with an adhesive on it, and the rest was a combination of an adhesive, mortar, and mortar with metal nails in it (Figure 13). Adhesives were, in both cases, dark gray, but in the second case, some tiles were fixed with an adhesive of a yellowish color.

Mortar and adhesive removal

Using a professional angle grinder with protection against dust, protection against overheating, and an adjustable number of revolutions seemed to us to be the best procedure here. Sanding with this sander turned out to be cheaper than if we had borrowed a concrete grinder or had to buy our own.

Our operations overheated the Makita grinder even though we regularly turned it off while sanding. We used one and a half reels. After destroying the Makita grinder, we procured a professional DeWalt grinder, which has already finished the job.

It was also shown that knocking off some of the material before grinding reduced the grinding time and the dust produced; however, this was not the case with Šilar's work, which involved removing the parts of tiles. It also turned out that working with two people is faster and safer than with one person and the other only supervising.

Furthermore, we can state that the system of holding the fragments with two wooden prisms and the lowest revolutions of the machine made it possible to safely grind even very small fragments that would otherwise be carried away and shot out by the machine's revolutions.

We also noticed that it is important to have the tiles laid on an even surface; two cracked when sanding on an uneven surface.

The material of the bare tiles was hard, and the tiles were sanded straight or with minor scratches; on the other hand, Šilar's tiles were soft, so the sanding wheel easily penetrated the tile itself (Figures 14, 15).

Figure 14. A groove in a tile from the work of Lubomír Šilar caused by a diamond-grinding disc

Figure 15. Minor scratches on the reverse of Stanislav Holý's artwork

Chipping with a mason's chisel turned out to be pretty physically demanding, but it was possible to remove a certain amount of mortar and adhesive tiles. An important factor was to visually monitor the tile and its momentum; if there was concern about high tension, then try a different direction or stop. Here, too, we had two tiles crack.

Scraping off the adhesives was quite effective, especially with yellow adhesives. However, it wasn't perfect, and even then, small remnants of adhesive were left on the back of the tiles (Figure 16). Yellowish adhesives were removed better after soaking them in the water, but there was no difference in soaking them just once or a couple of hours. Soaking grey adhesives hasn't affected the ease of their removal at all.

Citric acid and pressurized water proved wholly ineffective and did not visually remove the adhesives. Likewise, the rotating metal brushes mounted on the cordless drill proved ineffective.

Figure 16. Reverse of Stanislav Holý's tile. The remains of construction adhesive are light in color

Discussion

Disruption of the grout

There were multiple reasons why we haven't disrupted grout in the case of the removal of the first artwork. One reason was that the joints were very deep and at the same time very thin in diameter. There was also a feeling that if these tiles are so thick, the gray, probably cement based grout will not cause tile cracking. While in the case of flet glazed tiles we were afraid that tiles may crack if the grout is not disrupted and that's why in that case we were disrupting it even in a very small joints where the diamond disc could not fit. Our masons have commented that when disrupting thin glazed tiles without disrupting the grout, they are often cracking. This could be supported by videos on YouTube,^{24,25,26,27} but of course scientific investigation into this problem would be appreciated.

Tile removal

There were more cracked tiles among heavier Šilar work. This could be caused by the higher amount of stress within the tile caused by the jackhammer than in the case of the manual removal,

24 Rachel Martinelli, 'Quickly Remove Floor Tiles without Breaking', (YouTube, 2018), online:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TcfQP2-ZWdY>

25 AZ DIY Guy, 'Removing a Floor Tile without Breaking it - Re-Use Discontinued Tile', (YouTube, 2019), online:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EW6TxzLG6dQ>

26 SolarGirl Homestead, 'How to remove tile | Without breaking it', (YouTube, 2017), online:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PImEP7fRNqQ>

27 C.L.S. ALL-IN-ONE, 'How to remove Ceramic & Stone Tiles for Repair or Demo purposes', (YouTube, 2020), online: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p7cBazK4jrs>

but also by the fact that the first artwork tiles were porous. Further investigation into the tiles' origin and physical properties would contribute to the choice of removal method next time.

In the case of adhesives, we can clearly see that those with gray colors were based on cement, while those with yellow colors were more like adhesives based on synthetic resins.

In the case of tile removal, we see that detailed studies on stress distribution would be needed, and the masons have commented that if they were to remove another artwork of this kind, they would need to create their own tools.

As for tools, the most popular were putty knives, which can go further behind the tile. Thus, the scraper with a sharpened edge (Figure 17) was the most helpful tool and the tool that would inspire us to create a custom tool. We need a tool that is strong enough, long enough, and flat enough to get behind the large tile. With ordinary sheet metal, there is a problem with the destruction of the edge if it is tapped with a hammer for a long time. Therefore, welding a solid steel rod or column to a flat plate is the optimal solution. It would be very similar to the scraper with a sharpened edge, only with different widths, and it would be longer.

Figure 17. The scraper with a sharpened edge

Mortar and adhesive removal

It should be noted here that cleaning the tiles was not the project's primary goal. This was due to the need to align the tiles on the back so that they could be safely stacked on top of each other in the rack (so they didn't take up as much space) and to get rid of the excess weight so that they could be stacked more on top of each other.

However, even though the goal was not complete cleaning, we got a clear idea of how soft and hard tiles could be cleaned, which could be improved next time. If the tiles are to be re-installed, they will probably need to be cleaned, as the residue of the sand grains could act as an agent that causes the tiles to self-detach from the substrate when re-glued. Here, we can follow the practice of other conservationists and test some glazed tiles and submerge them in the solvent as reported by Mendes *et al.*²⁸ However, there is a question if it would work for both types of tiles.

Furthermore, it would be advisable to investigate the possibilities of re-attachment on the wall. However, we see as most important further research in the field of stress inside the tiles when cutting or grinding the material, which would determine the reason why the tiles crack and suggest improved cleaning options.

28 Marta T Mendes et al., 'In Situ Preservation and Restoration of Architectural Tiles, Materials and Procedures: Results of an International Survey', 2015.

Conclusion

We can conclude that more time for investigating the artworks on site and then careful removal would be appreciated next time. However with the gained knowledge, if having enough skilled workers on the size of an artwork, we can remove the work in a fast way. An essential mindset that some tiles may crack is vital for this. Our work shows that this mindset allowed us to remove the artwork. If some studies on the physical properties of tiles and internal pressure during removal are done before we have to engage in another removal, it would be appreciated if we could coin with that or even try the repetition of such research.

Another finding is that special tools would be helpful in removing tiles. However, tile cleaning and adhesive removal still need more investigation, as do restoration and new placement. Conservationists around the world possess certain knowledge. Some of the case studies were probably written in local languages, but our case studies are among the first to share knowledge and findings with a broader conservationist community as they are published in English.

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